

**PERCEIVED COMPETENCE AND EFFICACY AS
PREDICTORS OF LIFE SATISFACTION AMONG
ADOLESCENTS IN AKINYELE L.G.A OF IBADAN, OYO
STATE, NIGERIA.**

TABLE OF CONTENTS

TABLE OF CONTENTS

Title

Certification

Dedication

Acknowledgement

List of Tables

Abstract

Table of contents

CHAPTER ONE: INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background to the study

1.2 Statement of problem

1.3 Purpose of study

1.4 Relevance of study

CHAPTER TWO: THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK AND LITERATURE REVIEW

2.0 Overview

2.1 Theoretical framework

2.1.1 Self Determination Theory

2.1.2 The Theory of Reasoned Action

2.1.3 Self-Efficacy Theory

2.2 Review of Related Studies

2.3 Hypotheses

2.4 Operational Definition of Terms

CHAPTER THREE: METHODOLOGY

3.0 Overview

3.1 Research Design

3.2 Research Setting

3.3 Sample/Sampling Techniques

3.4 Research Instruments

3.5 Research Procedure

3.6 Statistical Analyses

CHAPTER FOUR: RESULTS

4.1 Demographic Information

4.2 Testing of Hypotheses

4.2.1 Hypothesis One

4.2.2 Hypothesis Two

4.2.3 Hypothesis Three

4.2.4 Hypothesis Four

CHAPTER FIVE: DISCUSSION, CONCLUSIONS, RECOMMENDATIONS, LIMITATIONS AND SUGGESTIONS FOR FURTHER STUDIES.

5.1 Discussion

5.2 Conclusions

5.3 Recommendations

5.4 Limitations

5.5 Suggestions for further studies

CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background to the Study

Life satisfaction is a generic concept that represents an individual's contentment with their own life. It is considered as one of the indicators which determine the quality of life, which includes physical, social, emotional and mental health. Several researchers have agreed with the conception that life satisfaction is subjective, evaluative and judgmental. Over the past decade, much attention has been on studying life satisfaction of individuals in various contexts, and the studies have conceptualised life satisfaction in multiple ways. Numerous studies have conceptualized it as a self-appraisal process by which a person compares and assess one's conditions of existence or quality of life with the self-referenced standards or chosen criteria (Diener et al., 1985). Diener Oishi and Lucas (2003) noted that less the variability or the incongruence between the achievement and desire, more significant is the sense of life satisfaction. Daig, Herschbach, Lehmann, Knoll, and Decker (2009) conceptualized it as a cognitive appraisal of one's life situation with the different domains of life.

Satisfaction with life is essential if an individual wants to handle challenging situations and circumstances and even to get benefits from them (Ammar et al., 2020; Casagrande et al., 2020). Participation in social activities is a must for a person's life

satisfaction (Nguyen et al., 2020; Zhang & Ma, 2020). Life satisfaction is an outcome achieved by the people through comparing what they possess and what they desire to possess (Altay & Avci, 2009). Life satisfaction is a significant element of academic performance. The students with a high level of life satisfaction exhibit greater flexibility and are less futile in facing academic hindrances. In contrast, students' low level of life satisfaction upsets their concentration and weakens their performance in the classroom. From the students' point of view, satisfaction implies that an individual is advancing towards significant life ambitions (Arias, 2004). Life satisfaction has a substantial relationship with student's classroom performance. Adolescents who have a high level of life satisfaction are more satisfied with their educational engagements (Duffy et al., 2012). In the absence of mental strain, life satisfaction is considered a substantial element of educational experiences and attainments among university students (Antaramian, 2015).

Life satisfaction is also connected with less educational anxiety, greater academic self-efficacy, higher perceived advancement towards achieving objectives, and constructive educational expectations (O'Sullivan, 2011). The boys and girls aged 15-17 years show an increase in life satisfaction when they move from school to successive academic paths. An increase in life satisfaction during puberty helps tackle critical academic problems such as handling different resources, educational issues, and locating an appropriate subsequent academic path whereas youth having low satisfaction with life tends to escape difficulties and cultivate an undesirable outlook towards academic life. Therefore, stable satisfaction with life may have credit for youth to persevere longer in dealing with school-related challenges (Salmela-Aro & Tuominen-Soini, 2010). There is a significant positive link between life satisfaction and positive emotional experiences such as contented, pleasant, good, joyful, and

happy but a significant negative link exists between life satisfaction and negative emotional experiences such as angry, bad, afraid, sad, and unpleasant across all age groups (Jovanović & Joshanloo, 2021).

Further, Life satisfaction as a core dimension of subjective well-being and a key measure of psychological health (Pavot & Diener, 2008) indicates strong relationship especially with intrinsic processes like personality and personal tendencies (Diener & Lucas, 1999). At the same time, life satisfaction deal with a variety of risk behaviours (e.g., alcohol and drug use, aggressive and violent behaviour, sexual activities), psychopathological symptoms (depression, anxiety, low self-efficacy, loneliness) and physical health indices (e.g., eating behaviour, exercise); that global life satisfaction mediates the impact of stressful life events. Furthermore, life satisfaction appears to operate as an intrapersonal strength that helps buffer against the development of psychopathology in the face of increasing stressful life events (McKnight, Huebner, & Suldo, 2002).

There are various factors that can contribute to life satisfaction among adolescents. However, this study is interested in how perceived competence and self-efficacy contributes to life satisfaction among adolescents in Akinyele L.G.A of Oyo State.

According to Tschannen-Moran, Hoy, and Hoy (2016), self-efficacy can be referred to as a reflection of an individuals' experience either success or failure besides their belief in their ability. Therefore, as a guideline, the researcher defined self-efficacy in as the belief an individual has on his/her ability to carry out certain given tasks.

Abbit (2011) describes self-efficacy as individual's belief on his or her ability to organize and execute the action to attain goods. This belief influences many aspects of behaviour that is the choice of action, amount and duration of effort and emotional response to success (Abbit, 2011). The action taken is based on individual's ability,

how long an attempt should be put in and how the individual manages emotional to succeed. That means Self-Efficacy Theory suggests the belief that concerns of one's ability that effects desired outcomes of thought and action (Abbit, 2011). The higher self-efficacy will produce a positive aura to support efforts, whereas, the lower self-efficacy affects decisions to continue the effort. An employee with high level self-efficacy tends to have high level of ethical work behaviour, than those with low level of self-efficacy. In other words, when employees have the belief in themselves to perform some activities tend to adhere with work ethics.

Apart from self-efficacy, another variable that could influence ethical work behaviour is managerial competence. Henderson (2000) defines competency as a combination of knowledge and skills required to successfully perform an assignment. Its attainment is evidenced by the ability of an individual to gather data, process it into useful information, access it and arrive at an appropriate and useful decision in order to initiate the actions necessary to accomplish the assignment in an acceptable manner.

Bandura (1977) defined self-efficacy as the combination of believing that an action will have a specific result and believing that one is able perform that action. These two beliefs together impact student behaviour, including effectively implementing strategies, which, in turn, positively influences academic performance (Pajares, 2002). For example, students who believe that completing readings before class will improve their performance and who believe they are able to complete the readings before class are more likely to proactively set aside time to read and, consequently, to complete the readings before class. Students who think that completing the readings is not an effective strategy are not likely to read the assignments. Additionally, students who think that they are unable to complete the readings before class, even if they think that

completing the reading assignments ahead of time would be an effective strategy, are unlikely to actually read the assignments.

Relatedly, adolescents with high self-efficacy tend to frame work demands as challenges rather than threats, which results in higher expectations for their performance as well as higher actual academic performance (Chemers, Hu, & Garcia, 2001). Easy success does not lead to a strong sense of self-efficacy because it does not foster the fortitude necessary to work through challenges. The belief that one can perform an action to bring about a specific result is gained through a cyclical process of persevering through challenging tasks and successfully completing them. Repeatedly surmounting obstacles convinces people that they are capable, increasing their self-efficacy and their persistence in tackling challenging problems (Bandura, 1997).

Apart from self-efficacy, another factor that could contribute to life satisfaction among adolescents is perceived competence. Competence is defined as intellectual, physical and manual, and interpersonal skills (Chickering, 1969; Chickering and Reisser, 1993). Competence is a three-tined pitchfork. Intellectual competence, physical and manual skills, and interpersonal competence are the tines. For development to occur there must be a handle. Sense of competence is attributed to one's confidence that one can cope with challenges and successfully accomplish tasks. The intellectual ability involves confidence in mastering job process and trainings, gaining intellectual capacity and building critical thinking skills. Most importantly, intellectual skills comprise the ability to reason, solve problems and participate in active job learning opportunities (Chickering & Reisser, 1993). Physical and manual abilities contribute to an individual's sense of competence. These skills come from a variety of activities being either work related or not. These skills are derived from

participation in organizational orientation and job training, attention to wellness, and involvement in performing tangible creations, and hands-on learning (Evans, et al., 1998, Chickering & Reisser, 1993).

Along with physical ability as a component of developing competence comes the facility to interact with others. An individual's interaction with others contributes to their level of interpersonal competence. Interpersonal skills include things like listening, self-disclosing, and participating in dialogue that brings insight and satisfaction (Chickering and Reisser, 1993). These skill sets assist individual's in building thriving friendships and relationships as well as prepare the individual for being an active citizen of an organization (Chickering and Reisser, 1993). Intellectual, physical and manual, and interpersonal abilities are all components of developing competence.

1.2 Adolescent's life satisfaction is more than just an outcome of various psychological states (e.g. positive affect, self-esteem), it is also an influential predictor of psychological states and psycho-social systems (e.g. depression, physical health) (Gilman, Meyers, & Perez, 2004). Life satisfaction among adolescents functions as a mediator and moderator between the environment and behavior (Suldo & Huebner, 2004), between the social support-involvement dimension of authoritative parenting and adolescent problem behavior. Further, support has been provided for the potential mediating role of life satisfaction between stressful life events and internalizing behavior (McKnight, Huebner, & Suldo, 2002). In addition satisfaction with life has been reported to be a buffer against negative effects of stress and the development of psycho-pathological behavior (e.g. Suldo & Huebner, 2004).

Such findings are highly significant to the promotion of positive development in any country or society (Proctor, Linley, & Maltby, 2008). Research report has also shown that life satisfaction as a construct has been central within the positive psychology (Gilman & Huebner, 2003) (b) adolescents who have low life satisfaction are more prone to violence (Valois, Zullig, Huebner, & Drane, 2006), destructive and risky behaviors, stealing and robbery (Valois, Zullig, Huebner, & Drane, 2001) and (c) past research in the area of life satisfaction has occurred within America, with most assessment measures being created and validated among American samples (Proctor et al., 2008) hence the need for the assessment of life satisfaction across cultures and specific groups beyond America. In response to the above, Oladipo and Olapegba (2012) were able to establish that there is low satisfaction with life among adolescents in Southwestern Nigeria. However, a limitation to their work was that there was no specification of the factors that may predict satisfaction with life among this population.

The focus of the present study therefore was to examine the psychological factors that would predict satisfaction with life among adolescents in Lagos state. That several benefits are associated with very high levels of life satisfaction has been recurrent in the literature, for example, Suldo and Huebner (2006) reported that adolescents with high levels of life satisfaction benefited from many positive outcomes, including: the highest level of social support from all sources, the lowest levels of neuroticism, significantly higher levels of academic, emotional, and social self-efficacy, the lowest emotional and behavioural problems, and superior interpersonal and cognitive functioning, than those with average and low life satisfaction. Gilman and Huebner (2006) found high levels of adolescent life satisfaction to be positively related to grade point average (GPA), interpersonal relations, parental relations, self-esteem, and

hope, and to be negatively related to poor attitude towards school, poor attitude towards teachers, social stress, anxiety, depression, and external locus of control. This study will focus on the role of self-efficacy and perceive competence in life satisfaction among adolescents in Akinyele LGA of Oyo State.

Research Questions

The following research questions will be answered at the end of the study;

1. Will self-efficacy have significant influence on life satisfaction among adolescents in Akinyele LGA of Oyo State?
2. Will perceived competence have significant influence on life satisfaction among adolescents in Akinyele LGA of Oyo State?
3. Will self-efficacy and perceived competence have significant joint and independent influence on life satisfaction among adolescents in Akinyele LGA of Oyo State?
4. Will there be significant gender difference in life satisfaction among adolescents in Akinyele LGA of Oyo State?

1.3 Purpose of Study

The broad objective of the study is to investigate the influence of perceived competence and self-efficacy on life satisfaction among adolescents in Akinyele LGA of Oyo State. The following specific objectives will be achieved at the end of the study;

1. To determine whether self-efficacy will have significant influence on life satisfaction among adolescents in Akinyele LGA of Oyo State;

2. To investigate whether perceived competence will have significant influence on life satisfaction among adolescents in Akinyele LGA of Oyo State;
3. To examine whether self-efficacy and perceived competence will have significant joint and independent influence on life satisfaction among adolescents in Akinyele LGA of Oyo State;
4. To know whether there will be significant gender difference in life satisfaction among adolescents in Akinyele LGA of Oyo State;

1.4 Significance of the Study

The findings of the study will be relevant in so many ways and to different stakeholders. This includes researchers, schools, parents and adolescents as individuals. To schools, the findings of the study will assist schools in identifying factors that could contribute to life satisfaction among adolescents. By knowing this, efforts will be made in adjusting those factors in a way that it will lead to having high level of life satisfaction.

To adolescents, an understanding of the role of self-efficacy and perceived competence in life satisfaction will assist employees in making decisive stands as regards life satisfaction especially among adolescents. Having the knowledge of this will subsequently contribute to higher efficiency and effectiveness in life for adolescents. In another way, the role of self-efficacy on life satisfaction will be emphasised. The findings will inform the practical recommendations that will be made to aid adolescents' development of adequate competencies.

Further, the findings of the study will contribute to research knowledge on the determinants of life satisfaction among adolescents.

CHAPTER TWO

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Theoretical Framework

2.1.1 Self-Determination Theory

The self-determination theory has its origin in the work of Deci and Ryan. It is a macro theory that is related to human development and the function of personality in different social contexts that takes interest in factors that either facilitate or forestall the assimilative and growth-oriented processes in people (Niemi & Ryan, 2009, p. 134). The theory suggest that individuals are motivated by qualitatively different factors and those factors are differentially related to outcomes (Deci and Ryan, 1985). It considers that motivation can be expressed through a continuum or exist along a continuum of increasing self-determination with three fundamental positions reflecting the degree of autonomy on which behaviors are based: amotivation and extrinsic and intrinsic motivation. Students' motivation for academic performance

varies in both strength (amount) and quality (nature), and both variations predict learning, achievement, and continuation to college (Deci & Ryan, 2002; Reeve, 1996). The theory distinguishes between these different types of motivation on the different reasons or goals that give rise to an action (Ryan & Deci 2000).

The self-determination theory consists of five inter-related mini-theories (Deci & Ryan, 2002): cognitive evaluation theory, organismic integration theory, causality orientations theory, goal contents theory, and basic needs theory. These five mini-theories played critical roles in the formulation and development of the self-determination theory, as such; discussion of this theory would be incomplete without description of those mini theories.

Cognitive evaluation theory focuses on determinants of motivation and proposes that autonomous motivation varies as function of one's feelings of competence and self-determination. Increase or decrease in either of the process leads to corresponding changes in motivation. It explains the effects of extrinsic factors or social contextual events (e.g., competition, deadlines, evaluations, imposed goals, praise, and rewards) on intrinsic motivation, behavior, and experience (Deci, 1975; Deci & Ryan, 1985). It also addresses the concept of internalization especially with respect to the development of extrinsic motivation (Deci & Ryan, 2002). Organismic integration theory proposes that externally regulated behaviors can be transformed to self-regulated behaviors (Deci & Ryan, 2002). It addresses the concept of internalization especially with respect to the development of extrinsic motivation (Deci & Ryan, 2002). Causality orientations theory was formulated to address individual differences in global (personality-level) motivational orientations; it describes how people incorporate social influences into their motivational styles (Deci & Ryan, 1985, 2002). Goal contents theory explains the impact of intrinsic and

extrinsic goals on human motivation and wellness (Kasser & Ryan, 1996). Finally, basic needs theory specifies a set of universal basic psychological needs that are essential nutrients for human beings 'optimal development and functioning psychological and physical health and social wellness (Deci & Ryan, 2002).

Amotivation represents the non-regulated extreme of the continuum, and it is characterized by the individual's perception of lack of control over events, incompetence and absence of purpose. A person is amotivated, when his or her behavior lacks intentionality (Ryan & Deci, 2000) such a person lacks motivation anyways. In extrinsic motivation (EM), the goal being chased constitutes the main driving force of behavior, which is divided into four subtypes of progressive regulation: external, introjected, identified, and integrated. In regards to the first of them, behaviors are enforced by others and are carried out to attain positive consequences or to obtain rewards while avoiding negative ones or punishment. Here, activities are not done out of pleasure or fun but to obtain rewards. In introjected regulation, behaviors are executed in order to improve one's self-esteem or to avoid anxiety and guilt that may arise for not carrying them out. As such, external demand becomes an internal representation which the person uses to approve or disapprove his or own behavior or action. In identified regulation, the individual chooses the activities by extrinsic motives (e.g., society values enrolling in superior studies). This behavior comes to play when the individual comes to value and judge behavior as being important and therefore performs behavior based on choice. The basis of the choice is not as a result of pressure from internal or external environment. The last subtype (integrated regulation) would appear only in adulthood, when individual needs and values converge with those expected by the social context (e.g., studying broadens one's horizons). According to Ryan & Deci (2000), extrinsic motivation is

thus a construct that is relevant whenever an activity is done in order to attain some reward. Extrinsically motivated behaviors are those where the controlling mechanism is easily seen (Deci 1985). An extrinsic orientation toward learning is characterized by a concern with external reasons for working, such as the judgment of others regarding one's performance, grades, or some anticipated reward (Goldberg, 1994). In a nut shell, extrinsically motivated behaviors are instrumental in nature and are usually performed as a means to an end.

Finally, intrinsic motivation (IM) occupies the autonomous regulation pole where the pleasure of executing behaviors by own choice prevails: activities becomes a goal themselves. In other words, intrinsically motivated behaviors are engage in for their own sake, which is, for the pleasure and satisfaction derived from their performance. Malone & Lepper (1987) defined intrinsic motivation as what people will do without external inducement. Fincham & Cain, (1986) viewed intrinsic motivation as patterns that have been associated with high perceived ability and control, realistic task analysis and planning and the belief that effort increases one's ability and control.

According to Deci Ryan (1987) Self-determined, intrinsic motivation emerges from the learner's own needs and desires rather than from outside pressures; and, it is this high-quality, intrinsic, self-determined motivation that most powerfully predicts positive school-related engagement and success (Hardre' & Reeve, 2003; Lau & Chan, 2003; Reeve, Bolt, & Cai, 1999; Vallerand, Fortier, & Guay, 1997).

According to self-determination theory, people need to feel the following in order to achieve such psychological growth; Competence; People need to gain mastery of tasks and learn different skills, a facilitator of intrinsic motivation, is the need to experience satisfaction in improving one's abilities (Deci & Ryan, 1985, 2000).

Relatedness; People need to experience a sense of belonging and attachment to other

people; it is the need to feel related to significant others (Deci & Ryan, 1985, 2000). Autonomous; People need to feel in control of their own behaviors and goals. It is the need to engage in self-directed behavior (Deci & Ryan, 1985, 2000). Autonomy implies that individuals experience choice in the initiation, maintenance, and regulation of their behaviors (Deci & Ryan, 1985, 2000). It has to do with the need to engage in self-directed behavior (Deci & Ryan, 1985, 2000). Autonomy implies that individuals experience choice in the initiation, maintenance, and regulation of their behaviors (Deci & Ryan, 1985, 2000). Deci and Ryan suggest that when people experience these three things, they become self-determined and able to be intrinsically motivated to pursue the things that interest them.

According to Deci, giving people extrinsic rewards for already intrinsically motivated behavior can undermine autonomy. As the behavior becomes increasingly controlled by the external rewards, people begin to feel less in control of their own behavior and intrinsic motivation is diminished. Deci also suggests that offering unexpected positive encouragement and feedback on a person's performance on a task can increase intrinsic motivation. Why? Because such feedback helps people to feel more competent, one of the key needs for personal growth. All in all, the satisfaction of these three psychological needs is hypothesized as being indispensable for the facilitation of self-determined motivation.

In essence, the whole idea of the self-determination theory is that though students are powerfully motivated intrinsically however students are not all intrinsically motivated for all tasks. Thus, students are intrinsically motivated, extrinsically motivated or not motivated at all (that is amotivation). Students can increase their motivation towards learning of tasks and content through internalization, the process of a student adopting increasing choice and value for learning, and ownership of the learning process

(Reeve, Deci, & Ryan, 2004; Ryan & Connell, 1989). Internalization is promoted through the support of three important student characteristics: autonomy, competence, and relatedness (Black & Deci, 2000; Ryan & Deci, 2000). Through internalization, a student becomes increasingly self-determined (versus other-determined or extrinsically pressured) (Deci, 1995; Reeve et al., 2004).

2.1.2 The Theory of Reasoned Action

The theory of reasoned action is another theory that can be applied in the explanation of career aspiration. The theory of reasoned action, (Ajzen & Fishbein, 1980) was first introduced in 1967 by Martin Fishbein in an effort to understand the relationship between attitude and behaviour. The theory posits that a person's intention to perform behaviour is the best predictor of subsequent behaviour. Intention, in turn, is predicted by attitude toward the behaviour and perceived social norms about performing the behavior. In other words, the theory attempts to explain the relationship between beliefs, attitudes, intentions and behavior. It therefore details the factors and inputs that result in any particular behavior. According to this theory, the most accurate determinant of behavior is behavioral intention and, the direct determinants of people's behavioral intentions are their attitudes towards performing the behavior and the subjective norms associated with the behavior. In essence, the theory is based on the assumption that behavior is the result of behavioral intentions, which are derived from two sources:

1. Attitude toward a behavior
2. Subjective norms

Attitude is determined by a person's beliefs about the outcomes or attributes of performing a specific behavior (that is, behavioral beliefs), weighted by evaluations of those outcomes or attributes. The subjective norm of a person is determined by

whether important referents (that is, people who are important to the person) approve or disapprove of the performance of a behavior (that is, normative beliefs), weighted by the person's motivation to comply with those referents (Ajzen & Fishbein, 1980; Montano & Kasprzyk, 2002). According to Montano and Kasprzyk (2002), the theory of reasoned action is successful in explaining behavior when volitional control is high.

As such, the theory provides another angle to understanding academic motivation. Based on this theory, motivation towards academic is seen as a function of the individual's behavioral intentions where behavioral intentions are a function of an individual's attitude toward the behavior and subjective norms surrounding the performance of the behavior. Attitude toward the behavior is defined as the individual's positive or negative feelings about performing a behavior. It is determined through an assessment of one's beliefs regarding the consequences arising from a behavior and an evaluation of the desirability of these consequences. Subjective norm is defined as an individual's perception of whether people important to the individual think the behaviour should be performed.

According to the theory of reasoned action, attitude and belief then becomes the major determinant of academic motivation of student; either to pursue a higher level of education or to put in more effort to perform better in a course. The theory provides a model outside of the psychological factors highlighted by the study. Whether an individual becomes positively motivated or otherwise is dependent according to this theory on; the individual's belief about the behaviour, his attitude toward this behaviour and his or her perception what the significant others think of the behaviour. Therefore an individual can be positively motivated if this factors are positively correlated however if it is the other way round, then reversed is the case.

Simply put, a belief that particular behaviour leads to a certain outcome and an evaluation of the outcome of that behaviour. If the outcome seems beneficial to the individual, he or she may then intend to or actually participate in a particular behaviour. This provides an explanation to the other aspect of academic motivation that has to do with the individual willingness to put in effort to do better in academic work. For example, if a student decides to be staying up at night, an extra effort to learn a particular course of subject, if the student eventually got an “A” in such a course, the academic motivation of that student becomes stronger, and he or she becomes more willing to sacrifice some sleeping time at night to learn other materials related to his or her academic work.

In conclusion, the theory of reasoned action (TRA) hypothesizes that behaviour is predicted by an individual’s intention to engage in a given behaviour. Intention, in turn, is predicted by two factors, the individual’s attitude towards the outcome of the behaviour and by the opinions of the person’s social environment, which is called the subjective norm (Fishbein and Ajzen, 1975). Very simply, the model looks like this:

Whether or not a person participates or intends to participate in any behaviour is influenced strongly by the people around them. These people may include friends or a peer group, family, co-workers, church congregation members, community leaders and even celebrities. Also, People may also be inclined (or not inclined) to participate in a behaviour based upon their desire to comply with others. Laws or rules prohibiting behaviour may have an impact on one’s attitude toward participating in behaviour. Ultimately, one’s attitude toward behaviour can lead to an intention to act

(or not to act as the case may be). This intention may or may not lead to a particular behavior.

2.1.3 Self-efficacy Theory

This theory can be attributed to Bandura (1987). According to Bandura, self-efficacy is defined as “an individual’s belief or conviction that they can successfully achieve at a designated level on an academic task or attain a specific academic goal” (Feltz et al. 2007). Bandura stated that self-efficacy played a role in determining how individuals felt, thought and motivated themselves, which then ultimately affected the behaviour and the outcome. On the basis of this theory, the present research assumes that when one’s self-efficacy towards research methods and statistics is high, he/she tends to put greater effort into studying the subject, which eventually results in a good grade. To put it in details, it means that when a student possesses a high self-efficacy towards research methods and statistics, it means that he/she has confidence in mastering the subject. With such a positive self-efficacy, this will simultaneously affect the student’s behaviour. Since the student thinks he/she is capable of doing well, this will lead to a series of favourable behaviours. For example, the student attends all the lectures and works hard on this subject. Derived from such favourable behaviours, it is expected that the student is likely to achieve a good result in the subject.

2.2 Review of Related Studies

As emphasized in the performed studies the fact that there is a positive relationship between life satisfaction and hope, interpersonal relationships, personal harmony (Huebner & Gilman, 2006), self-efficacy provides an important advantage in terms of both increase of life satisfaction and psychological and social development (Suldo & Huebner, 2006). Because, it was observed that there is a negative relationship between self-efficacy and social stress, anxiety, depression, outer control focus (Huebner &

Gilman, 2006) and violence (Valois, Paxton, Zullig, & Huebner, 2006). At this point, the belief in self-efficacy influences people's way of thinking and intrinsic reactions, and determines individuals' motivations and behaviour (Bandura, 1994). Individuals with high self-efficacy can be more comfortable and productive when they face hard working conditions. Those with low self-efficacy believe that what they will do is harder than reality. Such kind of a thought increases anxiety and stress, while it narrows the necessary viewpoint for a person to solve a problem ideally (Pajares, 2002). High- level of self-efficacy is of importance in terms of the fact that it determines psychological well-being (Magaletta & Oliver, 1999) and psychological harmony (Cutler, 2005). One has to solve the real life problems in order to get life satisfaction and to be happy (Dora, 2003).

Depending on all these results, high level of self-efficacy can contribute to the increase of activity level of young adults and to their being pleased with themselves, their lives and other conditions in their lives (certain living areas such as family, friends, and the environment being lived in). In our country, the studies of life satisfaction focus on primary school students (Kaya & Siyez, 2008), adolescents (Eryılmaz & Öğülmüş, 2010; Çivitçi & Çivitçi, 2009); university students (Tuzgöl-Dost, 2007); similarly, in studies of self-efficiency, although adolescents (Yardımcı & Başsakal, 2010), university students (Kaya & Dönmez, 2008), and young adults (Miçooğulları, Cengiz, Aşçı, & Kirazcı, 2010) were studied, the relationship between life satisfaction and self-efficacy were not sufficiently examined in the period of young adulthood.

High efficacy beliefs are also related to the expansion of satisfying social relations that bring about life satisfaction to an individual (Bandura, 1997). Therefore, social quality of life and satisfaction with accomplishments should be high in

self-efficacious individuals. Life satisfaction has been directly related to self-efficacy. Hampton's (2000) study of 100 Chinese individuals with spinal cord injuries found that self-efficacy was related to both the quality of life and the life satisfaction of the patients tested. Hampton (2000) found that "self-efficacy and health status were significantly correlated with life satisfaction" (p. 69). Furthermore, "the major contributor to life satisfaction was self-efficacy, which had the highest partial correlation with life satisfaction after health status and demographic variables were controlled" (p. 70).

People generally avoid tasks where self-efficacy is low, but undertake tasks where self-efficacy is high. When self-efficacy is significantly beyond actual ability, it leads to an overestimation of the ability to complete tasks. On the other hand, when self-efficacy is significantly lower than actual ability, it discourages growth and skill development. Research shows that the optimum level of self-efficacy is slightly above ability; in this situation, people are most encouraged to tackle challenging tasks and gain experience (Csikszentmihalyi, 1997). The Self-efficacy, affects every area of human endeavor. By determining the beliefs a person holds regarding his or her power to affect situations, it strongly influences both the power a person actually has to face challenges competently and the choices a person is most likely to make. These effects are particularly apparent, and compelling, with regard to behaviors affecting health (Luszczynska & Schwarzer, 2005).

Dewitz, Joseph and Walsh, Bruce (2002) this study focused on the relationship between self-efficacy (i.e. college, social and general) and college student's satisfaction. Results indicate that regression analysis and analysis of variance revealed that college self-efficacy was significantly associated with college satisfaction,

whereas the other two measures of self-efficacy (i.e. social & general) did not account for any unique additional variance.

Individuals' self-perception influences their satisfaction with life (Diener, 1984) and the ideal life that they envisage (Lyubomirsky, 2011). People with life satisfaction tend to be happy (Santos, Magramo, Oguan, & Paat, 2014). According to Diener (2013), experiencing happiness is not only an enjoyable result, but it also determines choice actions by the individual. Happiness can be 'pursued as an end in itself' (Tay, Kuykendall, & Diener, 2015, p. 839).

Occasionally, even the happiest of individuals also experience unpleasant feelings (Diener & Seligman, 2002), which could reduce their satisfaction with life. However, those with high self-efficacy may be better able to recover their life satisfaction within a short period despite their unpleasant circumstances. Self-efficacy influences the goals university students set for themselves (Akanni & Oduaran, 2018; Bartimote Aufflick et al., 2016; Coetzee & Oosthuizen, 2012; Davids, 2015; Huang, 2013). For instance, students with high self-efficacy work hard to attain personal goals which would translate into greater satisfaction with life and happiness.

Self-efficacy influences the level of challenges students set for themselves, the amount of effort they mobilize, and their persistence in the face of difficulties (Siu, Lu, & Spector, 2007). In the context of schooling, the transition from high school to the higher education environment may present self-perception challenges to some students (Matoti, 2011). This might be explained by the fact that a student's unpreparedness for the rigorous higher education environment may be compounded by the challenges of living away from their family (Prinsloo & Subotsky, 2011). However, positive self-perceptions facilitate goalsetting and satisfaction with life (Şahan, Tekin, Yıldız, Eraslan, Yıldız, Sim, & Yarar, 2012). This would be true of

university students (Myburgh, Poggenpoel, & HastingsTolsma, 2017) and also in their lived community (Scott, Yeld, & Hendry, 2007; Van Zyl & Rothmann, 2012).

Williams et al., (2010) reported self-efficacy to moderate the relationship between work context and psychological outcomes among public sector South African employees. Coetzee and Oosthuizen (2012) found self-efficacy to be unrelated to satisfaction with studies by learners in an open distance-learning environment in South Africa. However, De Bruin and Hughes (2012) found career decision self-efficacy to explain achievement scores among South African university students. Akanni and Oduaran (2018) found Nigerian university students' academic self-efficacy to be influenced by perceived social support from friends, academics and by attending organized orientation workshops.

Hosseini et al., (2011) in a study on elderly social support and positive relationship between social support and life satisfaction claimed that social support has a positive effect on physical, psychological, socioeconomic and quality of life and improves the quality of life, makes a good impression on the life and general assessment of life. Kiodo and Abella (2011) considered life satisfaction associated with social support; social interaction and a sense of belonging that is indispensable for the well-being would be increased.

Sarasyno (2010) in a study entitled with social capital and social well-being found that the socialized people in their life are supported socially, and social support leads to a higher life satisfaction and wellbeing. The results of Giolakty (2010) showed that perceived social support predicts life satisfaction 43 percent. He believes that spending time with family has a direct impact on people's satisfaction. He showed that the visuals that are supported by the friends indirectly affect the level of satisfaction and if the person understands himself better than his friends, his satisfaction would be

increased. Lent, Taveira, Sheu, and Singley, (2009) showed that the efficacy and environment protection, progress in goals and predict the life satisfaction (Narimani, Eini, Dehqan, Qolamzadeh and Saffarinia, 2013).

Existing empirical studies have shown that self-efficacy, as an essential protective factor of psychological resilience, can predict psychological resilience development (Chu et al., 2013). Bandura believes that self-efficacy is a hierarchical structure composed of general self-efficacy and task-related self-efficacy. The former is at the top, which refers to the general belief that an individual has in order to deal with challenges from different environments successfully or to deal with new things (Ersan et al., 2018; Li et al., 2019); the latter is at the bottom, which refers to the individual A specific belief that oneself can engage in specific activities related to a specific field of behavior (Li et al., 2019). Previous studies on middle school Left-behind children's self-efficacy paid more attention to task-related self-efficacy, such as emotional regulation self-efficacy, learning efficacy (Wang et al., 2017; Zhao & Wang, 2015), to middle school Left-behind. There are few studies on the general self-efficacy of children. However, task-related efficacy cannot represent general efficacy.

2.3 Hypotheses

1. Respondents with high level of self-efficacy will significantly report higher on life satisfaction compared to those with low level of self-efficacy.
2. Respondents with high level of perceived competence will significantly report higher on life satisfaction compared to those with low level of perceived competence.
3. Self-efficacy and perceived competence will have significant joint and independent influence on life satisfaction among adolescents in Akinyele LGA of Oyo State.

4. Male respondents will significantly report higher on life satisfaction compared to their female counterparts.

2.4 Operational Definition of Terms

Life Satisfaction: Life satisfaction (LS) is the way in which people show their emotions, feelings (moods) and how they feel about their directions and options for the future. This was measured using 5-item life satisfaction scale developed by Diener et al., (1985).

Self-Efficacy: This is described as a person's belief that they can exert control over their motivation and behaviour. This was measured using 10-item scale developed by Schwarzer (1997).

Perceived competence: Perceived competence is a self-perception of an individual in their capabilities and ability to control their environment and situation. This was measured using a 6-item perceived competence sub-scale developed by Rodgers et al., (2014).

CHAPTER THREE

METHODOLOGY

This section provides a description of the processes involved in eliciting and analyzing data for the study. This chapter will contain the research design, the study population, sample size and sampling technique, research instruments, administration of instruments and method of data analysis.

3.1 Research design

This study adopted a cross-sectional survey design. The rationale behind this option was based on the special features of the population under study using questionnaire for data collection. The focus of the study empirically examines self-efficacy and perceived competence as predictors of life satisfaction among adolescents in Akinyele LGA of Oyo State.

3.2 Research setting

The study was conducted in Akinyele LGA of Ibadan, Oyo State., Ibadan is regarded as the most populous city in Oyo State and the country's largest city by geographical area is located in the South-Western Geo-Political zone of Nigeria. With a population of over 6 million, using 3.2% growth rate from 2006 census figures, the 2010 estimated population for Akinyele LGA is 239,745. It is one of the eleven local

governments that make up the Ibadan metropolis. This LGA was created in 1976 and has its headquarters at Moniya. It shares boundaries with Afijio Local Government to the north, Lagelu Local Government Area to the east, Ido Local Government Area to the west and Ibadan North Local Government Area to the south. It occupies a land area of 464.892 square kilometers with a population density of 516 persons per square kilometer.

Specifically, the study will be conducted in selected secondary schools in Akinyele LGA of the Ibadan metropolis. This included both government and privately owned secondary schools this selected local government area.

3.3 Sample/Sampling Technique

The study adopted the purposive sampling technique. Specifically, the study selected three hundred and fifty (350) secondary school students in Akinyele LGA of Ibadan, Oyo State. Students cuts across three secondary schools; Ajibode Grammar School, Abadina College and Aponmode High School. However, three hundred and thirty five (335) were retrieved and utilized for data analysis.

3.4 Research instruments

SECTION A: measured the socio-economic status such as gender, age, family background, etc.

SECTION B: Life Satisfaction Scale

This is a 5-item scale developed by Diner et al, (1985). The scale was developed to measure the extent to which individuals are satisfied with events and happenings in their life and their environment. Response to the scale ranged as follows; Strongly agree, Agree, Slightly agree, Neither agree nor disagree, Slightly disagree, Disagree and Strongly disagree. The scale developers reported an internal consistency of 0.87.

SECTION C: Self-Efficacy Scale

This section contains 10 items measuring self-efficacy. This scale was developed by Schwarzer (1997). The items were adopted from Schwarzer (1997). The General Self-Efficacy Scale designed to assess optimistic self-beliefs to cope with a variety of difficult demands in life". The scale was originally developed in German by Matthias Jerusalem and Ralf Schwarzer in 1981 as a 20-item scale with two separate subscales of general self-efficacy and social self-efficacy. Example of an item on the scale is 'I can remain calm when facing difficulties because I can rely on my coping abilities'. The psychometric property of the scale has been established.

SECTION D: Perceived Competence Scale

This is a 6-item sub-scale of perceived competence scale developed by Rodgers et al., (2014). The scale was designed to assess individuals sense of intellectual and interpersonal competence. Intellectual competence refers to the ability for knowing oneself and accomplishing tasks which require mental ability. Interpersonal competence refers to the capacity to relate or to interact with others. The scale developer reported an adequate internal consistency of $\alpha = .882$.

3.5 Procedure

The researcher obtained letter of introduction from the Department of Psychology, Faculty of the Social Sciences, University of Lagos before proceeding to the field to gather data. Permission to conduct the research was sought from the (3) secondary school Principals by submitting a copy of the introductory letter to them. After approval a teacher was instructed to help with the process. The researcher was taken to the senior secondary classes by the class captain during lunch break and those who were interested and gave their consent participated in the study. They were given brief instructions concerning how to fill the questionnaire; and the exercise lasted for 4days. (Approximately (1) day for each school).

3.6 Statistical Analyses

Data were analyzed using SPSS (statistical packages for the Social Sciences) statistical software. Descriptive and inferential statistics were applied for the data collected. Hypotheses one, two and four were tested using t-test for independent samples, while hypothesis three was tested using multiple regression analysis at the 0.05 level of significance. This is best used to determine the extent and strength of the relationship between the independent and dependent variables.

CHAPTER FOUR

RESULTS

This chapter presents results on gathered data on perceived competence and efficacy as predictors of life satisfaction among adolescents in Akinyele Local Government Area of Oyo state. Data was gathered from three hundred and thirty five (n = 335) respondents.

4.1 Demographic Information

Table 4.1: Demographic Distribution

SN	Variable	Response	Frequency	Percentage
1	Age	Less than 15 years	105	31.3
		15-17 years old	220	65.7

		Above 17 years	10	3
2	Gender	Male	158	47.2
		Female	177	52.8
3	Family Background	Monogamous	287	85.7
		Polygamous	48	14.3
4	Parental Marital Status	Single parenting	31	9.3
		Married	266	79.4
		Divorced	31	9.3
		Separated	7	2.1
5	Class of Study	JSS 1	3	0.9
		JSS 2	8	2.4
		JSS 3	71	21.2
		SSS 1	175	52.2
		SSS 2	70	20.9
		SSS 3	8	2.4
	Total		335	100

Table 4.1 presents results on frequency distribution among adolescents in Akinyele local government area of Oyo state. Age distribution revealed that more of the respondents 220 (65.7%) indicated to be between 15 and 17 years old, 105 (31.3%) were less than 15 years old, while the other 10 (3%) were above 17 years old.

Gender distribution from Table 4.1 shows that more of the respondents 177 (52.8%) were females, while the other 158 (47.2%) were males. Family background frequency showed that more of the respondents 287 (85.7%) were from monogamous family, while the other 48 (14.3%) indicated to belong to a polygamous family.

According to parental marital status, more of the respondents 266 (79.4%) were married, 31 (9.3%) had single parent, another 31 (9.3%) were divorced, while the other 7 (2.1%) signified that their parents were separated.

Class of study showed that more of the respondents 175 (52.2%) indicated to be SSS 1 students, 71 (21.2%) were in JSS 3, 70 (20.9%) were SSS 2 students, 8 (2.4%) were JSS 2 students, another 8 (2.4%) were SSS 3 students, while the other 3 (0.9%) were JSS 1 students.

4.2 Testing of Hypotheses

Hypothesis One

Respondents with high level of self-efficacy will significantly report higher on life satisfaction compared to those with low level of self-efficacy. This was tested using t-test for independents samples and the result is presented on Table 4.2;

Table 4.2: T-test for Independent Samples Summary Table Showing Results on the Influence of Self-Efficacy on Life Satisfaction

Dependent	Self-Efficacy	N	Mean	SD	t	df	P
Life satisfaction	High	143	20.50	2.34	7.38	333	<.01
	Low	192	17.20	4.95			

Table 4.2 presents results on the influence of self-efficacy on life satisfaction among adolescents in Akinyele local government area of Oyo state. It is shown that self-efficacy was found to have significant influence on life satisfaction [$t(333) = 7.38; P < .01$]. Further, adolescents with high level of self-efficacy reported higher on life satisfaction (Mean = 20.50; SD = 2.34) compared to those with low level of self-efficacy (Mean = 17.20; SD = 4.95). This confirmed the stated hypothesis, hence was retained in this study.

Hypothesis Two

Respondents with high level of perceived competence will significantly report higher on life satisfaction compared to those with low level of perceived competence. This

was tested using t-test for independents samples and the result is presented on Table 4.3;

Table 4.3: T-test for Independent Samples Summary Table Showing Results on the Influence of Perceived Competence on Life Satisfaction

Dependent	Perceived Competence	N	Mean	SD	t	df	P
Life satisfaction	High	211	19.86	2.84	7.39	333	<.01
	Low	124	16.48	5.52			

Table 4.3 presents results on the influence of perceived competence on life satisfaction among adolescents in Akinyele local government area of Oyo state. It is shown that perceived competence was found to have significant influence on life satisfaction [t (333) = 7.39; P<.01]. Further, adolescents with high level of perceived competence reported higher on life satisfaction (Mean = 19.86; SD = 2.84) compared to those with low level of perceived competence (Mean = 16.48; SD = 5.52). This confirmed the stated hypothesis, hence was retained in this study.

Hypothesis Three

Self-efficacy and perceived competence will have significant joint and independent influence on life satisfaction among adolescents in Akinyele LGA of Oyo State. This was tested using multiple regression analysis and the result is presented on Table 4.4;

Table 4.4: Multiple Regression Summary Table Showing Results on the Joint and Independent Influence of Perceived Competence and Self-Efficacy as Predictors Life Satisfaction

Dependent	Predictors	β	t-value	P	R	R ²	F	P
Life satisfaction	Self-efficacy	.17	3.37	<.05	.55	.30	71.17	<.01
	Perceived competence	.45	8.58	<.01				

Table 4.4 presents results on the joint and independent influence of self-efficacy and perceived competence on life satisfaction among adolescents in Akinyele local government area of Oyo state. It is shown that self-efficacy and perceived competence was found to have significant joint influence on life satisfaction [$R = .55$; $R^2 = .30$; $F(2, 332) = 71.17$; $P < .01$]. When combined, self-efficacy and perceived competence accounted for about 30% variance in life satisfaction among adolescents in Akinyele Local Government Area of Oyo state. Also, self-efficacy ($\beta = .17$; $t = 3.37$; $P < .05$) and perceived competence ($\beta = .45$; $t = 8.58$; $P < .01$) were significant independent predictors of life satisfaction among adolescents. This confirms the stated hypothesis, hence was retained in this study.

Hypothesis Four

Male respondents will significantly report higher on life satisfaction compared to their female counterparts. This was tested using t-test for independent samples and the result is presented on Table 4.5;

Table 4.5: T-test for Independent Samples Summary Table Showing Results on Gender Difference in Life Satisfaction

Dependent	Gender	N	Mean	SD	t	df	P
Life satisfaction	Male	158	18.66	4.48	.21	333	>.05
	Female	177	18.56	4.27			

Table 4.5 presents results on gender difference life satisfaction among adolescents in Akinyele local government area of Oyo state. It is shown that there exists no significant gender difference in life satisfaction [$t(333) = .21$; $P > .05$]. This negates the stated hypothesis, hence was rejected in this study.

CHAPTER FIVE

DISCUSSION, CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This chapter presents the conclusive aspect of the research. Specifically, the following outline will be covered in this chapter; discussion, conclusion, recommendations and limitations of the study.

5.1 Discussion

The study investigated perceived competence and efficacy as predictors of life satisfaction among adolescents in Akinyele local government area of Oyo state, Nigeria. Hypothesis one stated that respondents with high level of self-efficacy will significantly report higher on life satisfaction compared to those with low level of

self-efficacy. This was tested using t-test for independent samples and it was discovered that self-efficacy was found to have significant influence on life satisfaction. Further, adolescents with high level of self-efficacy reported higher on life satisfaction compared to those with low level of self-efficacy. This confirmed the stated hypothesis, hence was retained in this study.

Similarly, Dewitz, Joseph and Walsh, Bruce (2002) this study focused on the relationship between self-efficacy (i.e. college, social and general) and college student's satisfaction. Results indicate that regression analysis and analysis of variance revealed that college self-efficacy was significantly associated with college satisfaction, whereas the other two measures of self-efficacy (i.e. social & general) did not account for any unique additional variance.

Hypothesis two stated that respondents with high level of perceived competence will significantly report higher on life satisfaction compared to those with low level of perceived competence. This was tested using t-test for independent samples and it was found that perceived competence was found to have significant influence on life satisfaction. Further, adolescents with high level of perceived competence reported higher on life satisfaction compared to those with low level of perceived competence. This confirmed the stated hypothesis, hence was retained in this study.

Hosseini et al., (2011) in a study on elderly social support and positive relationship between social support and life satisfaction claimed that social support has a positive effect on physical, psychological, socioeconomic and quality of life and improves the quality of life, makes a good impression on the life and general assessment of life. Kido and Abella (2011) considered life satisfaction associated with social support; social interaction and a sense of belonging that is indispensable for the well-being would be increased.

Sarasyno (2010) in a study entitled with social capital and social well-being found that the socialized people in their life are supported socially, and social support leads to a higher life satisfaction and wellbeing. The results of Giolakty (2010) showed that perceived social support predicts life satisfaction 43 percent. He believes that spending time with family has a direct impact on people's satisfaction. He showed that the visuals that are supported by the friends indirectly affect the level of satisfaction and if the person understands himself better than his friends, his satisfaction would be increased. Lent, Taveira, Sheu, and Singley, (2009) showed that the efficacy and environment protection, progress in goals and predict the life satisfaction (Narimani, Eini, Dehqan, Qolamzadeh and Saffarinia, 2013).

Hypothesis three stated that Self-efficacy and perceived competence will have significant joint and independent influence on life satisfaction among adolescents in Akinyele LGA of Oyo State. This was tested using multiple regression analysis and it was discovered that self-efficacy and perceived competence was found to have significant joint influence on life satisfaction. When combined, self-efficacy and perceived competence accounted for about 30% variance in life satisfaction among adolescents in Akinyele Local Government Area of Oyo state. Also, self-efficacy and perceived competence were significant independent predictors of life satisfaction among adolescents. This confirms the stated hypothesis, hence was retained in this study.

Also, Williams et al., (2010) reported self-efficacy to moderate the relationship between work context and psychological outcomes among public sector South African employees. Coetzee and Oosthuizen (2012) found self-efficacy to be unrelated to satisfaction with studies by learners in an open distance-learning environment in South Africa. However, De Bruin and Hughes (2012) found career

decision self-efficacy to explain achievement scores among South African university students. Akanni and Oduaran (2018) found Nigerian university students' academic self-efficacy to be influenced by perceived social support from friends, academics and by attending organized orientation workshops.

Hypothesis four stated that male respondents will significantly report higher on life satisfaction compared to their female counterparts. This was tested using t-test for independent samples and it was found that there exists no significant gender difference in life satisfaction. This negates the stated hypothesis, hence was rejected in this study.

5.2 Conclusion

The following conclusions were drawn based on the findings of the study;

Firstly, it could be concluded from this study that self-efficacy was a significant determinant of life satisfaction among adolescents in Akinyele local government area of Oyo state. Specifically, adolescents with high level of self-efficacy reported higher on life satisfaction compared to those with low level of self-efficacy.

Also, it was concluded from this study that perceived sense of competence was a significant determinant of life satisfaction among adolescents in Akinyele local government area of Oyo state. Adolescents with high level of perceived competence reported higher on life satisfaction compared to those with low level of perceived sense of competence.

In addition, when combined and considered independently, it could be concluded that self-efficacy and perceived sense of competence were predictors of life satisfaction among adolescents. In other words, the higher the self-efficacy and perceived sense of competence, the higher the life satisfaction among adolescents.

Finally, it could be concluded from this study that there exists no significant gender difference in life satisfaction among adolescents in Akinyele local government area of Oyo state.

5.3 Recommendations

The following recommendations were made based on the findings of the study;

Firstly, it was discovered that the higher the self-efficacy of adolescents, the higher their life satisfaction. It was therefore recommended that secondary school authorities including teachers and principals should take it as a point of duty to ensure that the efficacy of in-school adolescents is boosted by giving them the sense of having the ability to be what they want to become in life. Also, for out of school adolescents, it is recommended that concerned ministry and agency should have a designed program that will pick adolescents out of the street and subsequently introduce them to vocations and education that best suits their ability. This will directly or indirectly boost their self-efficacy and subsequently increase their level of life satisfaction.

Also, it was discovered that the higher the perceived competence, the higher the life satisfaction among adolescents. It is therefore recommended that concerned agencies should device means by which adolescents could believe more in themselves through increasing their self-worth. This will subsequently contribute to their increase in life satisfaction.

Further, it is recommended that schools and concerned agencies should recruit the services of psychologists. Psychologists will help identify the risk signs of poor life satisfaction of adolescents and be able to offer help when the need arises.

Finally, it is recommended that more studies should be carried out on other factors that can contribute to life satisfaction among adolescents. This will help offer more

practical recommendations on how best life satisfaction of adolescents can be achieved.

5.4 Limitations

There are series of limitations attached to the study. First limitation of the study was social desirability. Social desirability was observed among adolescents as some of them were conscious of their responses with fear that their responses will be utilized for other purposes. Also, the study was limited by financial constraints. The research did not get adequate fund in order to cover a wider scope. Finally the study was limited by time constraint.

5.4 Suggestion for further studies

Based on the findings of this research it is evident that there are numerous flaws due to insufficient data provided by participants. Future research should be longitudinal and carried out over a period of time to check for consistency in behaviours of students because there are certain extraneous variables that might have skewed their responses thus affecting the results. Also, it is important to conduct a similar research in other parts of the country i.e. (Lagos State, Osun State, Ekiti State) to help compare new contexts, cultures and family socio-economic backgrounds which all have their significance. Also it is necessary to put into consideration emerging theories posited and recent research work that would better validate the results of this research topic for comparative studies in the future.

REFERENCES

- Aldwin & Revenson. (1987). Relationships of job and family involvement, family social support, and work-family conflict with job and life satisfaction. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 81, 411-420.
- Andrews, F. M. & Withey, S. B. (1976). *Social indicators of well-being: America's perception of life quality*. New York: Plenum.
- Antoni, M. H., Lehman, J. M., Kilbourn, K. M., Boyers, A. E., Culver, J. L., Alferi, S. M., et al. (2001). Cognitive-behavioral stress management intervention decreases the prevalence of depression and enhances benefit finding among women under treatment for early-stage breast cancer. *Health Psychology*, 20, 20–32.
- Arbuckle, J. L., & Wothke, W. (2005). *Amos users' guide, version 6.0*. Chicago: SmallWaters.
- Baim & Donald. (2005). Social-cognitive conceptualization of attachment working models: Availability and accessibility effects. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 71, 94–109.
- Barnett, R. C., & Rivers, C. (1996). *She works, he works: How two-income families are happy, healthy, and thriving*. Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press.
- Becker, P. (1991). Theoretische Grundlagen. [Theoretical foundations]. In A. Abele & P. Becker (Hrsg.), *Wohlbefinden* (S. 13-49). Weinheim: Juventa.
- Becker, P.(1988). Ein Strukturmodell der emotionalen Befindlichkeit [A structural model of emotional mood]. *Psychologische Beiträge*, 30, 514-536.
- Becker, P.(1988). Ein Strukturmodell der emotionalen Befindlichkeit [A structural model of emotional mood]. *Psychologische Beiträge*, 30, 514-536. .

- Bisconti, T. L. & Bergeman, C. S. (1999). Perceived social control as a mediator of the relationships among social support, psychological well-being, and perceived health. *Gerontologist*, 39, pp 94-103.
- Bloomer & Kendall (1994). Lay theories of emotion: I. Conceptualization and measurement. *Imagination, Cognition and Personality*, 15, 249–271.
- Brennan, A., Chugh, S. & Kline, T. (2002). Traditional versus open office design: A longitudinal Field Study, *Journal of Environment and Behavior*, 34, 3, 279-299,
- Brief, P. & Roberson, I. (1989). Job attitude organisation: An exploratory study. *Journal of Applied Social Psychology*, 19, 717-727.
- Brill, M., Weidemann, S., Alard, L., Olson, J., & Keable, E. (2001) Disproving widespread myths about workplace design. Jasper, IN: Kimball International.
- Brüggegan, Garlipp, Haltenhof & Seidler (2007) Sociodemographic context of the AIDS epidemic in a rural area in Tanzania with a focus on people's mobility and marriage. *Sexually Transmitted Infections*, 78:97-105
- Byrne, B.M.A. (1989). primer of Lisrel: Basic Applications and Programming for Confirmatory Factor Analytic Model, New York: Springer – Verlag.
- Chen, H. (2008), “Job satisfaction among information system (IS) personel”, *Computers in Human Behavior*, 24: 105-118.
- Cimete, G., Gencalp, N.S., & Keskin, G. (2003). Quality of life and job satisfaction of nurses. *Journal of Nursing Care Quality*, 18(2), 151-158.
- Cinamon, R. G., & Rich, Y. (2005). Work-family conflict among female teachers. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 21(4), 365-378.
- Clarke, M., Koch, L., and Hill E. (2004), The work-family interface: Differentiating balance and fit, *Family and Consumer Sciences Research Journal*, 33(2).

- Clutterbuck, D. (2003). *Managing Work-life Balance: A Guide for HR in Achieving Organisational and Individual Change*. London: Chartered Institute of Personnel and Development.
- Cooper, C.L. (1999). Can we live with the changing nature of work? *Journal of Managerial Psychology*, 14: 569-72.
- Cooper, C.L. (1999). Can we live with the changing nature of work? *Journal of Managerial Psychology*, 14: 569-72.
- Cooper, D. R., & Emory, C. W. (1995). *Business Research Methods*. by Richard d Irwin.
- Copper, D. & Kurland, B (2002). Telecommuting, professional isolation, and employee development in public and private organisations. *Journal of organisational behavior*, 23, 511-532.
- Crooker, K., Smith, F., & Tabak, F. (2002). Creating WLB: A Model of Pluralism across Life Domains, *Human Resources Development Review*, 1(4): 387-419.
- Crouch, A., & Nimran, U. (1989). Office Design and the Behavior of Senior Managers, *Human Relations*,; 42; 139-155.
- David, C., (2003), *Managing Work-life Balance: A Guide for HR in Achieving Organisational and individual change*. chartered intitiute of personal and development, CIPD house, camp road, London.
- Denzin, N. K., & Lincoln, Y. S. (2000). *Handbook of Qualitative Research*.
- Detert, R. A., Caravella, T., Derosia, C., & Duquette, R. D. (2006). Reducing stress and enhancing the general well-being of teachers using T'ai Chi Chih® movements: A pilot study. *Californian Journal of Health*, 4(1), 162-173.

- Dev, G.N., (2012), Employees' perception on work life balance and its relation with job satisfaction in Indian public sector banks, *International Journal of Exclusive Management Research*,2(2), 1-13.
- Dex, S., Smith, C. & Winter, S. (2001). Effects of family-friendly policies on business performance (Working Paper No. 22). Cambridge: University of Cambridge, Judge Institute of Management.
- Edwards, A, Laar, D. V. Easton, S & Kinman,G. (2009). The Work-related Quality of Life Scale for Higher Education Employees, *Quality in Higher Education*, 15, 3,
- Fatima, G., & Rehman, W. u. (2012). Impact of Role (Ambiguity and Conflict) on Teaching Assistants' Satisfaction and Intention to Leave: Pakistani HEIs. *International Journal of Business and Management*;; 7(16).
- Fatima:, N., & Sahibzada:, D. S. (2012, April 30). An Empirical Analysis of Factors Affecting Work Life Balance among University Teachers: the case of Pakistan. *Journal of International Academic Research*, 12(1).
- Feather, N.T., & Rauter, K.A. (2004). Organizational citizenship behaviours in relation to job status, job insecurity, organizational commitment and identification, job satisfaction and work values. *Journal of Occupational and Organizational Psychology*, 77(1), 81-94.
- Fisher, D (2000). Mood and emotion while working: missing pieces of job satisfaction, *Journal of Organisational Behavior*, 21, 185-202.
- Fisher, S. (1994). *Stress in Academic Life : the mental assembly line*. Buckingham [England]: Buckingham [England] ; Bristol, PA, USA : Society for Research into Higher Education : Open University Press, 1994.

- Francis, J. J., Eccles, J. M., Johnston, J. M., Walker, J. A., Grimshaw, J. J., Foy, J. R., . . .
Bonetti, D. (2004). *Constructing Questionnaires Based On The Theory Of Planned Behaviour A Manual For Health Services Researchers*. University Of Newcastle, Centre For Health Services Research. United Kingdom: Centre For Health Services Research.
- Frone, M. R., & Rice, R. W. (1987, January). Work-Family conflict: The effect of job and family involvement. *Journal of Organizational Behavior*, 8(1), 45-53.
- Gajendran, S., & Harrison, A. (2007). The good, the bad, and the unknown about telecommuting: Meta-analysis of psychological mediators and individual consequences. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 92(6), 1524–1541.
- Gall, M. D., Gall, J. P., & Borg, W. R. (2003). *Educational Research: An Introduction*.
- Gash, V., Mertens, A., Romeu, G. L., (2010), Women between part-time and full-time work: The influence of changing hours of work on happiness and life-satisfaction, SOEP Papers No. 268, DIW Berlin.
- Golden, Timothy D., & John, V. (2005). "The Impact of Extent of Telecommuting on Job Satisfaction: Resolving Inconsistent Findings." *Journal of Management* 13(2):301-318.
- Greenhaus, H., Collines, M, & Shaw, D. (2003). The relation between work-family balance and quality of life. *Journal of Vocational Behavior*, 63, 510-531
- Greenhaus, J. H., Collins, K. M., & Shaw, J. D. (2003). The relation between work–family balance and quality of life. *Journal of Vocational Behavior*, 63, 510-531.
- Gregory, A. and Milner, S. (2009), Editorial: Work-life Balance: A Matter of Choice, *Gender, Work & Organization*.

- Grover, L., & Crooker, J. (1995). Who appreciates family-responsive human resource policies: The impact of family-friendly policies on the organisational attachment of parents and non-parents. *Personnel Psychology*, 48, 271–288.
- Gutek, B. A., Searle, S., & Klepa, L. (1991). Rational versus gender role explanations for work-family conflict. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 76(4), 560-568.
- Hanglberger, D., (2010), *Arbeitszufriedenheit und flexible Arbeitszeiten – Empirische Analyse mit Daten des Sozio-oekonomischen Panels*, SOEP Papers No. 304, DI Berlin.
- Hanif, A.M., (2002). X-efficiency Analysis of Commercial Banks in Pakistan: A Preliminary Investigation, *The Pakistan Development Review*,41(4) 567-580.
- Hayman, J. (2005, july). Psychometric Assessment of an Instrument Designed to Measure Work Life Balance. *Research and Practice in Human Resource Management*, 13(1), 85-91.
- Herzberg, F., Mausner, B., & Snyderman, B. (1959), *The Motivation to Work*, John Wiley and Sons Inc., New York, NY.,
- Hill, J., Ferris, M. & Martinson, V. (2003) 'Does it matter where you work? a comparison of
- Hill, J., Hawkins, J., Ferris, M., & Weitzman, M. (2001). Finding an extra day a week: The positive effect of job flexibility on work and family life balance. *Family Relations*, 50(1), 49–58.
- Hogarth, T., Hasluck, C., & Pierre, G. (2001). Work – Life Balance 2000: Results from the Baseline Study, *Labour Market Trends*, 109(7): 371-3.
- Hoppock, R. (1935). *Job Satisfaction*. New York and London :: Harper and brothers.

- how three work venues (traditional office, virtual office, and home office) influence aspects of work and personal/family life', *Journal of Vocational Behavior*, Vol. 63, No. 2, pp. 220-241.
- Idiab, A., Haron, M., Sabri, M., and (2011), Commercial Banks & Historical Development, *Journal of Applied Sciences Research*. 7(7): 1024-1029.
- Igbaria, M., Greenhaus, J.H., & Parasuraman, S. (1991). Career Orientations of MIS Employees: An Empirical Analysis, *MIS Quarterly*, 15(2): 151-169.
- Ives, S. & Ferdinands, R. (1974). Working in a Landscaped Office. *Personnel Practice Bulletin*, no. 30: 126-41.
- Johnson, B., & Christensen, L. (2010). *Educational Research: Quantitative, Qualitative and Mixed Approaches*. (4 ed.). SAGE.
- Kenny D.T., Carlson, J.G., McGuigan, F.J., & Sheppard, J.L. (2000). *Stress and health: research and clinical applications.*, Amsterdam: Harwood Academic Publishers.
- Kossek, E. E. (2005). Workplace policies and practices to support work and families. In S. Bianchi, L. Casper, & R. King (Eds.), *Work, family health and well-being* (pp. 97–116). Mahwah, NJ: Lawrence Erlbaum Associates.
- Kuo, Y.F., & Chen, L.S. (2004). Individual demographic differences and job satisfaction among Information Technology personnel: An empirical study in Taiwan. *International Journal of Management*, 21(2), 221-231.
- Lambert, S.J., (2000). Added Benefits: The Between Work Life Benefits and Organizational Citizenship Behaviour. *Academy of Management Journals*, 43(5), 801 – 815.
- Lazarus, R. S. (1966). *Psychological Stress and the Coping Process*. McGraw-Hill.

- LoBiondo-Wood, G., & Haber, J. (1998). *Nursing Research: Methods, Critical Appraisal, and Utilization*. (4th, Ed.) Mosby.
- Mahamuda, P.M., and Nurul, K. M. M. (2011), Factors Affecting Employee Job Satisfaction of Pharmaceutical Sector, *Australian Journal of Business and Management Research*, .1(9), 113-123.
- Malik, M.I., Gomez, S.F., Ahmad, M., and Saif, M. I., (2010), Examining the relationship of Work Life Balance, Job Satisfaction and Turnover in Pakistan, *International Journal Sustainable Development*, 2(1) 27-33.
- Manisha, P., (2013), A Comparative Study of Work Life balance in various Industrial Sector in Pune Region, *International Journal of Marketing, Financial Services & Management Research*. 2(3).
- Marczyk, G., DeMatteo, D., & Festinger, D. (2005). *Essentials of Research Design and Methodology*. New Jersey , Canada: John Wiley & Sons, Inc.
- Maren, R., Pitarelli, F., and Cangiano, F. (2013), Work-life balance and job satisfaction among teachers, *Interdisciplinary Journal of Family Studies*, 18, 51-72.
- Maslow, A. H. (1954). *Motivation and personality* (1st ed.).
- McNall, L. A., Masuda, A. D., & Nicklin, J. M. (2010). Flexible Work Arrangements, Job Satisfaction, and Turnover Intentions: The Mediating Role of Work-to-Family Enrichment. *The Journal of Psychology*, 144(1), 61-81.
- Mosadeghrad, A.M. (2003). The Role of Participative Management (Suggestion System) in Hospital Effectiveness and Efficiency. *Research in Medical Sciences*, 8(3): 85-89.

- Mowday, R.T., Porter, L.W. & Steers, R.M. (1982). *Employee- Organization Linkage: The Psychology of Commitment, Absenteeism, and Turnover*. New York: Academic Press.
- Nadeem, M. S., & Abbas, D. Q. (2009, May). The Impact of Work Life Conflict on Job Satisfactions of Employees in Pakistan. *International Journal of Business and Management*, 4(5), 63-83.
- Nazari, K., & Emami, M. (2012). The Investigation Of The Relation Between Job Stress And Job Satisfaction (Case Study In Faculty Members Of Recognized Public And Private Universities In The Province Of Kermanshah). *Advances in Natural and Applied Sciences*, 6(2), 219-229.
- Ning, T. (2004). *Antecedents And Consequences Of Role Stress In Hospitality Industry*. National University Of Singapore, Department Of Management And Organization, Singapore.
- Noor, F., and Shamim, A., (2012), An Empirical Analysis of Factors Affecting Work Life Balance among University Teachers: the case of Pakistan, *Journal of International Academic Research*, .12(1).
- Noor, K.M. (2011), Work-Life Balance and Intention to Leave among Academics in Malaysian Public Higher Education Institutions, *International Journal of Business and Social Science*, 2(11).
- Okpara, J.O. (2004). Personal characteristics as predictors of job satisfaction: An exploratory study of IT managers in a developing economy. *Information Technology & People*, 17(3), 327-338.
- Onwuegbuzie, A. J., & Leech, N. L. (2005, june). Taking the “Q” Out of Research: Teaching Research Methodology Courses Without the Divide Between

- Quantitative and Qualitative Paradigms. *International Journal of Methodology*, 39(3), 267-295.
- Organ, D.W. (1997). Organizational citizenship behavior: it's construct cleanup time. *Human Performance*, 10(2): 85-97.
- Oshagbemi, T. (2003). Personal correlates of job satisfaction: Empirical evidence from UK universities. *International Journal of Social Economics*, 30, (11/12), 1210-1232.
- P.Robbins, S., & Coulter, M. (2004). *Management* (8th ed.). Prentice Hall.
- Polit, D. F., & Hungler, B. P. (1999). *Nursing Research: Principles and Method* (6 ed.). Lippincott.
- Qayyum, c. (2013, June). Job Satisfaction of University Teachers across the Demographics (A Case of Pakistani Universities). *Bulletin of Education and Research*, 35(1), 1-15. Retrieved from www.bia.ca.
- Quarat-ul-ain, khattak, M. A., & Iqbal, N. (2013, April). Impact of Role Conflict on Job Satisfaction, Mediating Role of Job Stress in Private Banking Sector. *Interdisciplinary Journal Of Contemporary Research In Business*, 4(12), 711-722.
- R.Gayathiri, & Ramakrishnan, D. L. (2013, January). Quality of Work Life – Linkage with Job Satisfaction and Performance. *International Journal of Business and Management Invention*, 2(1), 01-08.
- Rani, S., Kamalanabhan, & Selvarani. (2011). Work / Life Balance Reflections On Employee Satisfaction. *Serbian Journal of Management*, 6(1), 85-96.
- Rehman, Hafeez, Ahmed, and Saima, (2008), An Empirical Analysis of the Determinants of Bank Selection in Pakistan, *Pakistan Economic and Social Review*. 46(2), 147-160.

- Resourcing, H. (2005), The case for work/life balance: Closing the gap between policy and practice. Hudson Australia and New Zealand available on www.hudson.com
- Robbins, S.P., Odendaal, A., & Roodt, G. (2003). Organisational behaviour (9th ed.). Cape Town: Prentice-Hall International.
- Sabra, N.M., Abbas, and Qaisar, (2009), The Impact of Work Life Conflict on Job Satisfactions of Employees in Pakistan, International Journal of Business and Management. 4(5).
- Sageer, Rafat,A., Sameena, Agarwal, and Puja, (2012), Identification of Variables Affecting Employee Satisfaction and their Impact on the Organization, Journal of Business and Management, 5, 32-39.
- Saif, D. M., Malik, M. I., & Awan, M. Z. (2011, September). Employee Work Satisfaction and Work - Life Balance: A Pakistani Perspective. Interdisciplinary Journal Of Contemporary Research In Business, 3(5), 606-617.
- Saif, Iqbal,M., Malik, Imran,M., Zahid, M.,(2011), Employee Work Satisfaction and Work - Life Balance: A Pakistani Perspective, Interdisciplinary Journal of Contemporary Research in Business, 3(5).
- Saira, A., Zahid, M, and Mehboob, A., (2013). Impact of Work-Life Conflict and Work over Load onEmployee Performance in Banking Sector of Pakistan, Middle-East Journal of Scientific Research. 14 (5), 688-695.
- Sakthivel, D.& Jayakrishnan, J.(2012). Work Life Balance and Organizational Commitment for Nurses. Asian Journal of Business and Management Sciences, 2 (5), 01-06.

- Sakthivel, R., Kamalanabhan, and Selvarania, (2011), Work Life Balance Reflections on Employee Satisfaction, Serbian Journal of Management. 6 (1), 85 - 96.
- Sakthivel, R. & Kamalanabhan (2011). Work life balance reflections on employee satisfaction. Serbian Journal of Management 6 (1): 85-96.
- Saleem, Saba. Majeed, Sadia. Aziz, Tariq and Usman, (2013), Determinants of Job Satisfaction among Employees of Banking Industry at Bahawalpur, Journal of Emerging Issues in Economics, Finance and Banking, 1(2).
- Scholarios, D., & Marks, A. (2006). Worklife balance and the software worker, Human Resource Management Journal, 14(2): 54-74.
- Scholarios, D., & Marks, A. (2006). Worklife balance and the software worker. Human Resource Management Journal, 14(2): 54-74.
- Sehgal and Shallu, (2012), Job Satisfaction of Bank Employees in Shimla, International Journal of Marketing, Financial Services & Management Research 1(7).
- Smucker, M.K., Whisenant, W.A., & Pedersen, P.M. (2003). An investigation of job satisfaction and female sports journalists. International Sports Journal, 49(7/8), 401-407.
- Stanton, P. M., Noor, K. M., & Young, S. H. (2009). Work-life Balance and Job Satisfaction : A study among Academics in Malaysian Higher Education Institutions. 14th Asia Pacific Management Conference (APMC): Enhancing Sustainability in the Asia Pacific: Entrepreneurship and Innovation (pp. 1-15). Surabaya, Indonesia: Airlangga University.
- Tennant, C. (2001). Work-related stress and depressive disorders. Journal of Psychosomatic Research, 697-704.

Tombari, N., & Spinks, N. (1999). The Work – Family Interface at the Royal Bank Financial Group: Successful, Solutions – a Retrospective Look at Lessons Learned, *Women in Management Review*, 14(5): 186- 94.

Tombari, N., & Spinks, N. (1999). The Work – Family Interface at the Royal Bank Financial Group: Successful, Solutions – A Retrospective Look at Lessons Learned, *Women in Management Review*, 14(5): 186-94.

Tuli, F. (2010, September). The Basis of Distinction Between Qualitative and Quantitative Research in Social Science: Reflection on Ontological, Epistemological and Methodological Perspectives. *Ethiop. J. Educ. & Sc.*, 6(1), 97-10.

Umukoro F.G., Kuye, O.L., & Sulaimon, A.H.A. (2009). Matching Strategies to Situations: Programmed and adaptive implementation approaches, *Serbian Journal of Management*, 4 (2): 259 - 272.

APPENDIX

UNIVERSITY OF IBADAN FACULTY OF THE SOCIAL SCIENCES DEPARTMENT OF PSYCHOLOGY

Dear respondent,

This questionnaire is purely and strictly for academic and research purpose. Please be rest assured that confidentiality of all of your responses to the items that follows is highly guaranteed and in no account will it be disclosed to anyone not authorized.

Thanks for your cooperation.

SECTION A

Please tick the appropriate box applicable to you

1. Sex: Male () Female ()
2. Age: _____
3. Family background: Monogamous [] Polygamous []
4. Parental marital status: Single parent [] Married [] Divorced [] Separated []
5. Class of study: _____

SECTION B - Life satisfaction

Kindly respond to the following items using the response key; 1 – Strongly disagree, 2 – Disagree, 3 – Slightly disagree, 4 – Neither agree nor disagree, 5 – Slightly agree, 6 – Agree, 7 - Strongly agree

SN	Item	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
1	In most ways my life is close to my ideal							
2	The conditions of my life are excellent.							
3	I am satisfied with my life.							
4	So far I have gotten the important things I want in life.							
5	If I could live my life over, I would change almost nothing.							

SECTION C - Perceived Competence

Please carefully read the following statement and respond to each item. Please tick using the following rating **SD= Strongly Disagree; D=Disagree; U=Undecided; A=Agree; SA= Strongly Agree.**

S/N	Items	SD	D	U	A	SA
1	I meet people comfortably.					
2	I read fast enough to handle assignments at college.					
3	I have little difficulty with college work.					
4	I feel empathy for others.					
5	I will need tutoring in a specific course.					
6	I respond to the needs of others.					
7	I feel swamped with academic work.					
8	I will graduate with honors.					
9	I will fail at least one college course.					

10	I make friends easily.					
11	I will achieve my academic goals.					
12	I get along with most of the people I meet.					
13	Professors underrate my ability.					
14	I am afraid of making mistakes.					
15	I trust the decisions I make.					
16	I can cope with life's ups and downs.					
17	I welcome criticism as an opportunity for growth.					
18	I am not afraid to show my emotions.					
19	I converse casually and seriously with friends.					
20	I don't mind if friends know my weaknesses.					
21	I talk with professors easily about my concerns					
22	Rate your intellectual capacity					
23	Rate your interpersonal skill level					

SECTION D - Self-Efficacy

Instruction: Read each of the statement carefully and tick the option that indicates the extent to which each statement applies to you.

SN	Item	Not at all true	Barely true	Moderately true	Exactly true
1.	I can always manage to solve difficult Problems if I try hard enough.				
2.	If someone opposes me, I can find means and ways to get what I want.				
3.	It is easy for me to stick to my aims and accomplish my goals.				
4.	I am confident that I could deal efficiently with unexpected events				
5.	Thanks to my resourcefulness, I know how to handle unforeseen situations.				
6.	I can solve most problems if I invest the necessary effort.				
7.	I can remain calm when facing difficulties because I can rely on my coping abilities.				
8.	When I am confronted with a problem, I can usually find several solutions.				
9.	If I am in a bind, I can always think of something to do.				
10.	No matter what comes my way, I'm usually able to handle it.				